

The relationship between information literacy and entrepreneurial capabilities of sports science graduated students of Tehran universities

Maryam Mokhtari Dinani¹ *- Saeide Tatari

Abstract

The purpose of this research was the relationship between information literacy with entrepreneurial capabilities of Physical Education Graduated students of Tehran Universities. The Statistical population were all of the Physical Education graduated students of Tehran Universities (N=1100). According to Morgan table, 270 people were chosen with sampling stratified random method. Information literacy standard questionnaire (2003) and Durham entrepreneurial capabilities standard questionnaire (1991) were used to collect data. The results showed there was significant relationship between information literacy with entrepreneurial capabilities of Physical Education Graduated students of Tehran Universities. Also, based on regression analysis, there were significant relationships between components of the information literacy and entrepreneurial capabilities and information literacy can predict entrepreneurial capabilities. In addition, the two components of "the ability to effective access to information" and "the ability to use targeted information" had the most ability to significant prediction for entrepreneurship capability of sport sciences graduated students in Tehran universities. Considering the effective role of "the ability to use targeted information" in predicting of student entrepreneurship capacity, it is necessary that universities to provide specialized information related to entrepreneurship and employment to students interested in sport entrepreneurship.

Keywords: Entrepreneurial Capabilities, Information literacy, Student

Mokhtari Dinani, M., Tatari, S. (2019). The Relationship Between Information Literacy and Entrepreneurial Capabilities of Sports Science Graduated Students of Tehran Universities. *Research on Educational Sport*, 6(15): 95-116. (Persian). Doi: 10.22089/RES.2017.4532.1338

¹. Assistant Professor of Alzahra University, Email: M.mokhtaridinani@alzahra.ac.ir